

MULTIOBJECTIVE DUALITY WITH $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -INVEXITY

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Under $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invexity assumptions on the functions involved, weak, strong, and converse duality theorems are proved to relate properly efficient solutions of the primal and dual problems for a multiobjective programming problem.

1. Introduction

The notion of η -invexity was originally introduced by Hanson [6] who showed that, for a nonlinear programming problem whose objective and constrained functions are η -invex (all with respect to the same η), the Karush-Kuhn-Tucker necessary optimality conditions are also sufficient. The term invex (for invariant convex) was coined by Craven [2] to signify the fact that the invexity property of a function is invariant under certain types of coordinate transformations. Evidently, convex functions, in general, do not possess this property.

Various properties, extensions, and applications of η -invex functions are discussed in [1, 2, 7] among others. Later the concept of $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invexity has been introduced by Zalmai [11], which generalizes the notion of invexity.

Recently programs with several conflicting objectives have been extensively studied in the literature. Introducing the concept of proper efficiency of solutions, Geoffrion [5] proved an equivalence between multiobjective program with convex functions and a related parametric (scalar) objective program. Using this equivalence, Weir [9] formulated a dual program for a multiobjective program having differentiable convex functions. Subsequently, Egudo [4] and Weir [9] proved duality results for a differentiable multiobjective program with pseudoconvex/quasiconvex functions. Das and Nanda [3] have studied the duality theorems of Mond-Weir type for a multiobjective programming problem with semilocally invex functions. Xu [10] has studied mixed-type duality in multiobjective programming problems.

In the present paper, duality results (weak, strong, and converse duality theorems) are proved for multiobjective programming problem under $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invexity assumptions on the functions involved.

2. Preliminaries

In [5], Geoffrion considered the following multiobjective programming problem:

(VP)

$$\text{Minimize}_{x \in X} f(x), \quad (2.1)$$

where $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^p$ and X is an open subset of \mathbb{R}^n , and minimization means obtaining efficient solutions in the following sense.

A point $\bar{x} \in X$ is an efficient solution for $f = (f_1, f_2, \dots, f_p)$ if there is no $x \in X$ such that $f(x) \leq f(\bar{x})$ and $f(x) \neq f(\bar{x})$.

An efficient solution $\bar{x} \in X$, for which there exists a scalar $M > 0$ such that for each $i = 1, 2, \dots, p$, we have

$$\frac{f_i(x) - f_i(\bar{x})}{f_j(\bar{x}) - f_j(x)} \leq M \quad (2.2)$$

for some j such that $f_j(x) > f_j(\bar{x})$ and $f_i(x) < f_i(\bar{x})$ for $x \in X$, is called a properly efficient solution of (VP) (see Geoffrion [5]). Geoffrion [5] proved the following results.

LEMMA 2.1. *If for fixed $0 < \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^p$, \bar{x} is an optimal solution of the parametric programming problem*

(P $_\lambda$)

$$\text{Minimize}_{x \in X} \lambda^T f(x), \quad (2.3)$$

where $0 < \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is a vector, then \bar{x} is a properly efficient solution of the multiobjective problem (VP).

LEMMA 2.2. *If X is convex and $f_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, p$, are all convex functions, then \bar{x} is a properly efficient solution for (VP) if and only if \bar{x} is an optimal solution of the parametric programming problem (P $_\lambda$) for some $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^p$ with strictly positive components.*

Recently Hanson and Mond [7] have generalized Lemma 2.2 to invex functions. They have shown that if $f_i, i = 1, 2, \dots, p$, are differentiable invex functions with respect to the same $\eta(x, u)$ (n -dimensional) for $x \in X, u \in X$, then \bar{x} is properly efficient solution in the multiobjective programming problem (VP) if and only if \bar{x} is an optimal solution of the parametric programming problem (P $_\lambda$) for some $\lambda \in \mathbb{R}^p$ with strictly positive components.

A differentiable function $f(x)$ is said to be invex (see [1, 6]) at a point $u \in X$ over X if there exists $\eta(x, u) \in \mathbb{R}^n$ such that

$$f(x) - f(u) \geq \eta(x, u)^T \nabla f(u) \quad \forall x \in X. \quad (2.4)$$

Here ∇f denotes the gradient of f and the subscript “ T ” stands for the transpose of a vector. Later the concept of $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invexity has been studied by Zalmai (see [11]), which generalizes the notion of invexity function.

Definition 2.3. A differentiable function $h : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}$ is called $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex with respect to vector-valued functions η and θ if there exists some real number ρ such that for all $x, u \in X$,

$$h(x) - h(u) \geq \eta^T(x, u) \nabla h(u) + \rho \|\theta(x, u)\|^2. \tag{2.5}$$

If $\rho > 0$, then $f(x)$ is called strongly $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex, if $\rho = 0$, we obviously get the usual notion of invexity, and if $\rho < 0$, then $f(x)$ is called weakly $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex. It is clear that

$$\text{strongly } \rho - (\eta, \theta)\text{-invex} \implies \text{invex} \implies \text{weakly } \rho - (\eta, \theta)\text{-invex}. \tag{2.6}$$

Definition 2.4. h is said to be $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -pseudoinvex with respect to vector-valued functions η and θ , if there exists some real number ρ such that for all $x, u \in X$

$$\eta^T(x, u) \nabla h(u) \geq -\rho \|\theta(x, u)\|^2 \implies h(x) \geq h(u). \tag{2.7}$$

Definition 2.5. h is said to be $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -quasi-invex with respect to vector-valued functions η and θ if there exists some real number ρ such that for all $x, u \in X$,

$$h(x) \leq h(u) \implies \eta^T(x, u) \nabla h(u) \leq -\rho \|\theta(x, u)\|^2. \tag{2.8}$$

3. Duality

Consider the following multiobjective programming problems:

(PVP) Minimize $x \in X f(x)$ subject to $g(x) \leq 0$,

(DVP) Maximize $x \in X, \lambda, y, f(u) + y^T g(u)e$ subject to $\nabla \lambda^T f(u) + \nabla y^T g(u) = 0, y \geq 0, \lambda \geq 0, \lambda^T e = 1$,

where $f : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^p, g : X \rightarrow \mathbb{R}^m, y \in \mathbb{R}^m, \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^p$, and e is p -tuple of 1's. Thus parametric (scalar) programming problems corresponding (PVP) and (DVP) are

(PC $_{\lambda}$) Minimize $x \in X \lambda^T f(x)$ subject to $g(x) \leq 0$,

(DC $_{\lambda}$) Maximize $x \in X, y \lambda^T f(u) + y^T g(u)$ subject to $\nabla \lambda^T f(u) + \nabla y^T g(u) = 0, y \geq 0$,

respectively. In programming problems (PC $_{\lambda}$) and (DC $_{\lambda}$), the vector $0 < \lambda \in \mathbb{R}^p$ is predetermined. In [4], Egudo and Hanson proved weak and strong duality theorems between (PVP) and (DVP) for invex functions. We prove the following duality theorems.

THEOREM 3.1 (weak duality). *Let S be the feasible region for the primal problem (PVP), that is, $S = \{x \in X, g(x) \leq 0\}$. Let (u, λ, y) be a feasible point in the dual problem (DVP) such that $\lambda^T f$ is $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex at $u \in S$ and $y^T g$ is $\rho_1 - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex at $u \in S$ with $\rho + \rho_1 \geq 0$. Then*

$$\lambda^T f(x) \geq \lambda^T f(u) + y^T g(u) \quad \forall x \in S. \tag{3.1}$$

Proof. Since $\lambda^T f$ is $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex at u over S and $y^T g$ is $\rho_1 - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex at u over S , we have

$$\begin{aligned} \lambda^T f(x) - \lambda^T f(u) &\geq \eta^T(x, u) \nabla (\lambda^T f(u)) + \rho \|\theta(x, u)\|^2, \\ y^T g(x) - y^T g(u) &\geq \eta^T(x, u) \nabla (y^T g(u)) + \rho_1 \|\theta(x, u)\|^2, \end{aligned} \tag{3.2}$$

that is,

$$\begin{aligned} & \{\lambda^T f(x) + y^T g(x) - \lambda^T f(u) - y^T g(u) \\ & \geq \eta^T(x, u)[\nabla(\lambda^T f(u)) + \nabla(y^T g(u))] + (\rho + \rho_1)\|\theta(x, u)\|^2\}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.3}$$

Now since (u, λ, y) is feasible in (DVP), we have $\eta^T(x, u)[\nabla(\lambda^T f(u)) + \nabla(y^T g(u))] = 0$ and $y^T g(x) \leq 0$ for all $x \in S$, therefore inequality (3.3) reduces to

$$\lambda^T f(x) \geq \lambda^T f(u) + y^T g(u) + (\rho + \rho_1)\|\theta(x, u)\|^2. \tag{3.4}$$

Again $\rho + \rho_1 \geq 0$, so

$$\lambda^T f(x) \geq \lambda^T f(u) + y^T g(u) \quad \forall x \in S. \tag{3.5}$$

□

THEOREM 3.2 (strong duality). *Let \bar{x} be a properly efficient solution of the multiobjective programming problem (PVP) at which a constraint qualification is satisfied. Then there exists $(\bar{\lambda}, \bar{y})$ such that $(\bar{x}, \bar{\lambda}, \bar{y})$ is a feasible solution in the programming problem (DVP) and $y^T g(\bar{x}) = 0$. If also for each feasible $(u, \bar{\lambda}, y)$ in the dual programming problem (DVP), $\bar{\lambda}^T f$ is $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex and $y^T g$ is $\rho_1 - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex at u over the primal feasible region $S = \{x \mid x \in X : g(x) \leq 0\}$ with $\rho + \rho_1 \geq 0$, then $(\bar{x}, \bar{\lambda}, \bar{y})$ is a properly efficient solution of the dual programming problem (DVP) and the objective values are equal.*

Proof. Since a constraint qualification [8] (also see Ben-Israel and Mond [1]) is satisfied at \bar{x} , then, from Kuhn-Tucker necessary conditions [5], there exists $(\bar{\lambda}, \bar{y})$ such that $(\bar{x}, \bar{\lambda}, \bar{y})$ is a feasible solution in the programming (DVP) and $y^T g(\bar{x}) = 0$. Hence, objective function values are equal. Also since for each feasible $(u, \bar{\lambda}, y)$ in the dual programming problem (DVP), $\bar{\lambda}^T f$ is $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex and $y^T g$ is $\rho_1 - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex at u over S , then

$$\begin{aligned} \bar{\lambda}^T f(x) - \bar{\lambda}^T f(u) & \geq \eta^T(x, u)\nabla(\bar{\lambda}^T f(u)) + \rho\|\theta(x, u)\|^2, \\ y^T g(x) - y^T g(u) & \geq \eta^T(x, u)\nabla(y^T g(u)) + \rho_1\|\theta(x, u)\|^2, \end{aligned} \tag{3.6}$$

that is,

$$\begin{aligned} \{\bar{\lambda}^T f(x) + y^T g(x) & \geq \bar{\lambda}^T f(u) + y^T g(u) \\ & + \eta^T(x, u)[\nabla(\bar{\lambda}^T f(u)) + \nabla(y^T g(u))] + (\rho + \rho_1)\|\theta(x, u)\|^2\}. \end{aligned} \tag{3.7}$$

But $[\nabla(\bar{\lambda}^T f(u)) + \nabla(y^T g(u))] = 0$, therefore

$$\bar{\lambda}^T f(x) + y^T g(x) \geq \bar{\lambda}^T f(u) + y^T g(u) + (\rho + \rho_1)\|\theta(x, u)\|^2. \tag{3.8}$$

Since $y \geq 0$ and $g(x) \leq 0$, for all $x \in X$, we have $y^T g(x) \leq 0$, for all $x \in S$. Hence, for all feasible $(u, \bar{\lambda}, y)$ in the dual programming problem (DVP), we have

$$\bar{\lambda}^T f(x) \geq \bar{\lambda}^T f(u) + y^T g(u) + (\rho + \rho_1)\|\theta(x, u)\|^2 \quad \forall x \in S. \tag{3.9}$$

As $\rho + \rho_1 \geq 0$, so

$$\bar{\lambda}^T f(x) \geq \bar{\lambda}^T f(u) + y^T g(u) \quad \forall x \in S. \tag{3.10}$$

By assumption, \bar{x} is feasible in the primal (PVP) and we have shown that $(\bar{x}, \bar{\lambda}, \bar{y})$ in the dual (DVP) we have

$$\bar{\lambda}^T f(u) + y^T g(u) \leq \bar{\lambda}^T f(\bar{x}). \tag{3.11}$$

Now (3.11) implies that for $\bar{\lambda}$, (\bar{x}, \bar{y}) solves the parametric problem (DC_λ) . Since $\bar{\lambda} > 0$, from Geoffrion’s [5] sufficient conditions, we conclude that $(\bar{x}, \bar{\lambda}, \bar{y})$ is properly efficient for the problem (DVP). \square

4. Converse duality

In this section, we study the converse duality theorem.

THEOREM 4.1 (converse duality). *Let $(\bar{x}, \bar{\lambda}, \bar{y})$ be a feasible solution for the dual problem (DVP) such that $\bar{\lambda} f$ is $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex at \bar{u} on S and $\bar{y}^T g$ is $\rho_1 - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex at \bar{u} over the primal feasible region $S = \{x \mid x \in X : g(x) \leq 0\}$ with $\rho + \rho_1 \geq 0$. Suppose there exists $\bar{x} \in S$ such that $\bar{\lambda}^T f(\bar{x}) = \bar{\lambda}^T f(\bar{u}) + \bar{y}^T g(\bar{u})$. Then \bar{x} is properly efficient solution of (PVP). If also for each feasible $(u, \bar{\lambda}, y)$ in the dual programming problem (DVP), $\bar{\lambda}^T f$ is $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex at u over S and $y^T g$ is $\rho_1 - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex at u over the primal feasible region $S = \{x \mid x \in X : g(x) \leq 0\}$ with $\rho + \rho_1 \geq 0$, then $(\bar{x}, \bar{\lambda}, \bar{y})$ is also properly efficient of the dual multiobjective programming problem (DVP).*

Proof. By Theorem 3.1 we have

$$\bar{\lambda}^T f(x) \geq \bar{\lambda}^T f(\bar{u}) + \bar{y}^T g(\bar{u}) \quad \forall x \in S. \tag{4.1}$$

Now since there exists $\bar{x} \in S$ such that

$$\bar{\lambda}^T f(\bar{x}) = \bar{\lambda}^T f(\bar{u}) + \bar{y}^T g(\bar{u}), \tag{4.2}$$

so

$$\bar{\lambda}^T f(x) \geq \bar{\lambda}^T f(\bar{x}) \quad \forall x \in S. \tag{4.3}$$

Since $x \in S$, (4.3) implies that for $\bar{\lambda}$, \bar{x} is an optimal solution of the parametric programming (PC_λ) . As $\bar{\lambda} > 0$, from Geoffrion’s sufficient conditions, \bar{x} is properly efficient solution of the primal multiobjective programming problem (PVP).

Again because $\bar{\lambda}^T f$ is $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex and $y^T g$ is $\rho_1 - (\eta, \theta)$ -invex at u over S with $\rho + \rho_1 \geq 0$, we have, for each feasible $(u, \bar{\lambda}, y)$ in the dual programming problem (DVP),

$$\bar{\lambda}^T f(x) \geq \bar{\lambda}^T f(u) + y^T g(u), \quad \forall x \in S, \tag{4.4}$$

and because $\bar{x} \in S$ and $\bar{\lambda}^T f(\bar{x}) = \bar{\lambda}^T f(\bar{u}) + \bar{y}^T g(\bar{u})$, it follows that

$$\bar{\lambda}^T f(u) + y^T f(u) \leq \bar{\lambda}^T f(\bar{x}) = \bar{\lambda}^T f(\bar{u}) + \bar{y}^T g(\bar{u}), \tag{4.5}$$

and (4.5) holds for all feasible $(u, \bar{\lambda}, y)$ in the dual programming problem (DVP). This implies that for $\bar{\lambda}$, (\bar{u}, \bar{y}) is an optimal solution of the parametric programming problem (DC_{λ}) . Since $\bar{\lambda} > 0$, it now follows from Geoffrion's [5] sufficient condition that $(\bar{x}, \bar{\lambda}, \bar{y})$ is a properly efficient solution of the dual programming problem (DVP). \square

Concluding remark. As $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invexity/pseudoinvexity is a generalization of invexity, multiobjective variational problem and multiobjective control problem under $\rho - (\eta, \theta)$ -invexity will orient future research of the authors.

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References

- [1] A. Ben-Israel and B. Mond, *What is invexity?* J. Austral. Math. Soc. Ser. B **28** (1986), no. 1, 1–9.
- [2] B. D. Craven, *Generalized concavity and duality*, Generalized Concavity in Optimization and Economics (S. Schaible and W. T. Ziemba, eds.), Academic Press, New York, 1981, pp. 473–489.
- [3] L. N. Das and S. Nanda, *Proper efficiency conditions and duality for multiobjective programming problems involving semilocally invex functions*, Optimization **34** (1995), no. 1, 43–51.
- [4] R. R. Egudo and M. A. Hanson, *Multiobjective duality with invexity*, J. Math. Anal. Appl. **126** (1987), no. 2, 469–477.
- [5] A. M. Geoffrion, *Proper efficiency and the theory of vector maximization*, J. Math. Anal. Appl. **22** (1968), 618–630.
- [6] M. A. Hanson, *On sufficiency of the Kuhn-Tucker conditions*, J. Math. Anal. Appl. **80** (1981), no. 2, 545–550.
- [7] M. A. Hanson and B. Mond, *Self-duality and invexity*, FSU Statistics Report M 716, Department of Statistics, Florida State University, Florida, 1986.
- [8] O. L. Mangasarian, *Nonlinear Programming*, McGraw-Hill, New York, 1969.
- [9] T. Weir, *Proper efficiency and duality for vector valued optimization problems*, J. Austral. Math. Soc. Ser. A **43** (1987), no. 1, 21–35.
- [10] Z. Xu, *Mixed type duality in multiobjective programming problems*, J. Math. Anal. Appl. **198** (1996), no. 3, 621–635.
- [11] G. J. Zalmai, *Generalized sufficiency criteria in continuous-time programming with application to a class of variational-type inequalities*, J. Math. Anal. Appl. **153** (1990), no. 2, 331–355.

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